

Correlations between egg masses and plant height and tiller density were positive and significant. Taller and denser canopies were more preferred for egg deposition. BR4112-2B-6 was least preferred, probably because it had the shortest plants and produced fewer tillers (Table 2).

Leaf blade width and foliage color had no apparent influence on egg deposition. ■

Table 2. Yellow stem borer egg masses deposited on deepwater rice entries in a nethouse. Pot study, BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1989.

Entry	Reaction ^a in 1988	Plant height (cm)	Tiller density (no./pot)	Egg mass density (no./pot) ^b
Sadapankaich-HR40	HP	73.5	31.3	6.5 a
DWC-B-184	LP	67.0	26.4	5.1 ab
BR4112-2B-5	HP	62.5	21.2	4.0 ab
Habiganj Aman II	LP	54.6	27.2	2.9 b
BR4112-2B-6	LP	46.4	17.4	2.1 b

^a LP = less preferred, HP = highly preferred in the field. ^b Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Red stripe, a newly reported disease of rice in Vietnam

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A new disease on rice in the Mekong Delta has the typical symptom of an orange stripe extending from both ends of an oval lesion (Fig. 1).

The lesion usually begins as a small water-soaked yellow spot 0.1-0.3 cm in size. It gradually turns orange-red within 2-3 d. The stripe develops from both ends of the spot, enlarging rapidly under moist, hot conditions, and may extend the entire length of the leaf. Numerous stripes may occur on the same leaf. An infected leaf may die and dry out. Red stripe was also observed on the leaf

sheath. In severe cases, the entire plant may be killed 10-15 d before harvest.

Although the disease has been found on 20-d-old seedlings, it normally is most severe after heading, and can cause 50% yield reduction.

Red stripe was first observed in 1988, when thousands of hectares of rice were affected in Tien Giang Province. Since then, it has been readily found. In the 1990 summer and autumn season, thousands of hectares were affected by the disease. Most promising short-

duration varieties, such as IR64, IR66, IR19660, IR42, MTL 61, and MTL 58, were severely affected.

We isolated *Curvularia lunata* on PDA by culturing 0.1-0.3 cm leaf pieces cut from new spots. We obtained 65-75% fungus 3 to 5 d after culturing.

Inoculum was prepared from cultures grown in the same medium. We inoculated 35- to 45-d-old seedlings by spraying. Inoculated plants were placed in a moist chamber for incubation. Typical lesions appeared 7 d after incubation at 30-32°C, and 15 d after incubation at 26-28°C. Lesions developed on both 35- and 45-d-old seedlings.

When we sectioned diseased tissues, we observed abundant species and mycelium of *C. lunata* in the vascular systems (Fig. 2a,b). ■

1. Typical red stripe lesions on inoculated plants.

2. a) Conidia, conidiophores, mycelia of *C. lunata* PDA culture. b) Spores of *C. lunata* on PDA culture.

Correlations between light trap catches, field populations of yellow stem borer (YSB), and lunar phase

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As part of a larger study on the regional dynamics of rice insect pests, we examined the relationship between YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* catches in small kerosene light traps and populations in adjacent fields.

Nine traps were within a 17,000-ha area of uniform double cropping in Nueva Ecija Province, Philippines, during 1981 wet season. Near the median planting date of surrounding fields, experimental plots of IR52 were